

The Praxis of Good Governance in Wale Okediran's *The Boys at The Border* and Joseph Edoki's *The Upward Path*

Prof. Jude A. Agho

*Department of English, Faculty of Arts,
Ambrose Alli University, Nigeria*

&

Isaac O. Atere, PhD

*Department of English,
Faculty of Arts, Ambrose Alli University, Nigeria*

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0311-0518>

Abstract

*This paper attempts a discussion on governance in Nigeria vis a vis the military and civilian experiences, which without much contestation, can be summarily identified as failed attempts in meeting the yearnings and aspirations of Nigerians. Literature from this background, has been addressing issues of dysphoric governance with a claustrophobic outlook. Again, the campaign for a positive canvas about Nigeria by creative artists has necessitated the praxis of good governance. Two Nigerian novels are used to strike a balance. Wale Okediran's *Boys at the Border* dwells on systemic failure in Nigeria; thereby affirming the pessimism about Nigeria. Joseph Edoki's *The Upward Path* philosophically portrays the dividends of good governance. This paper, therefore, submits that both authors in their different trail of thoughts artistically advocate good governance.*

Key Words: Praxis, good governance, *Boys at the Border*, *The Upward Path*.

Introduction

Nigerian literature cannot debar the potentials of history in its literary creativity and contextualizing of criticism. The past, present and even the future resonate in shaping the texture of literary engagements in Nigeria. The history of governance in Nigeria has shown that governance, either by military or civilian administration, is faced with deception and self-centeredness. Regrettably, this is evident in the various coups and counter-coups that toppled successive military regimes, and the political hullaballos in the forms of assassinations, violent campaigns, massive electoral malpractices, inconclusive elections and the travesty of justices in the judicial system that have eclipsed civilian administrations in Nigeria. Those in the corridors of power often capitalize on these with the purported claim of fighting for national unity and against corruption while they are on a voyage of financial aggrandizement, thereby plunging the nation into poverty and debt. To corroborate this, Femi Osofisan asserts that:

First by the fiat of colonial masters, then under the post-independence local rulers, we have had no other experience of governance but of unfortunate leadership. Virtually all our governments have been illegitimate ... either it is a government of civilians or who have rigged themselves into power ... or it is a government of soldiers who have shot themselves into power. (47-48)

As such, governance in Nigeria is best described as dysphoric. These historical experiences of governance in Nigeria have informed the engagements of most Nigerian writers such as Wole Soyinka's *Interpreters, Season of Anomy, The Man Died*; Chinua Achebe's *No Longer at Ease, A Man of the People, Anthills of the Savannah, There was a Country*, etc.

This has had negative influences on the literature emanating from the gory and uneasy governance. According to Charles Nnolim: "in Anglophone, West Africa, the politically attuned novelist revealed in bad light the subversion of post-independence hopes and promises by those who were banked upon to redress the wrongs inflicted by the colonial masters" (64). This problem of leadership and bad governance in Nigeria needs to be addressed by channelling a new song of good governance to create a positive image about Nigeria and conscientizing the citizens on the need for the right attitude towards governance. Therefore, Nnolim pontificates that: "We need a new spiritual reorientation, a new creative hope to give artistic impetus to a new world order. Our writers, in this new epoch of globalism dominated by a technologically oriented new order, must create a new Africa, a new spirit of optimism, and show the African continent as full of promises, able to feed its teeming population, with healthy and vibrant people, not dependent on Europe and America for sustenance" (3). On this note, Jude Agho asserts that: "... it is useful to encourage African leaders to pay attention to the development of the continent and imbibe the rubrics on good governance, good leadership, transparency, accountability and eschew corruption ..." (72).

Good governance, as opined by Madhav Gadgil, "has much to do with the ethical grounding of governance and must be evaluated with reference to specific norms and objectives as may be laid down (202). These ethical values are summarized as transparency, trust, responsiveness, accountability and participation (Ikola-Norbacka et al 79). Comparatively, Wale Okediran's *The Boys at the Border* and Joseph Edoki's *The Upward Path* contrastively engage Nigerian literature at both ends. While *Boys at the Border* tailors the nihilistic view about Nigeria on dysphoric governance, *The Upward Path* canvasses good governance.

The Praxis of Good Governance in *The Boys at the Border* and *The Upward Path*

The Boys at the Border focuses on the depravity of the Nigerian society. Issues of systemic corruption in the Nigerian Customs Service, Police force and the inept leadership of military administration in Nigeria are symptomatic of the parlous state of governance in Nigeria as highlighted by Okediran. Practically, these vices are the springboard upon which betrayal, killings and revenge thrive in any society. Okediran, in this text, gives a pictorial overview of the decay and high level of corruptive synergy between most Customs officers and smugglers.

The novel opens on a sad note with the death of Samuel Adigwe, a Customs officer who is shot dead by one of the smugglers. The corrupt tendencies and bribe taking leads to the death of the Customs officer. The culprit explains that: "... the third truck has a flat tyre and we were changing it, the young Customs man intercepted us. Despite my offer of two thousand naira for the three trucks, he insisted on taking six thousand naira. I told him I was broke but he persisted. Then he ordered me at gunpoint ... Then I became afraid and I...shot him"

(20). Samuel died while negotiating bribe with a smuggler. This act of bribe-taking among uniformed men is what Okediran tries to correct. Today in Nigeria, Customs officer milk money from smugglers and in the process promote the trend. Again, Customs officers while negotiating bribe have killed many innocent citizens.

Furthermore, within the convoluted scenario of the death of Samuel, the military that has just taken over the government of the nation, invites the Director of Customs, Mr. Emodi to an urgent meeting on how to secure fund for government and block all means of smuggling in the nation. To this end, the Brigadier, the President and Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of Nigeria charges the Director of Customs to mount formidable surveillance in all borders, to ensure no one smuggles cocoa, groundnut, textile and others, which have now become the country's major source of fund as a result of the dwindled crude oil price. Here, the issue of betrayal, sycophancy and the contest of supremacy between the military and customs are typified.

The Customs boss, having received order from the president, calls a meeting with his deputies to relate the same. However, the response from some of the deputies such as Alhaji Jibo, Mallam Hanayo and Alhaji Shamir is ridiculous and uncomely to their boss. They berate the director for allowing himself to have been harassed by the president. Jibo with his fawning behaviour- gives sarcastic comments about the military and their wives alleging that they are the brain behind most smuggling in the country: "I'm personally disappointed that the director allowed that stupid Brigadier to insult the Customs as if most of the smuggling being done in the country is not by army officers and their wives" (13).

These deputy directors also accuse the military of being dictatorial and autocratic in their dealings. Again, they feel that the Brigadier president is of lesser educational qualification to be ordering the Customs boss who is a degree holder. Jibo's comments are ploys to derail the Customs boss while working on his psyche to fall before the military president. Although, Mr. Emodi is advised by Deputy Comptroller, Dele Adepeju, to tread with caution, the Customs boss falls into the scheme of Jibo. Having been invited by the president on the progress of the Custom in clamping down smugglers, he (Emodi) allows his emotion to take over his sense of decorum. He blatantly accuses the military of being responsible for smuggling and also proves to substantiate his claim by calling on his deputies to attest to this accusation. There is a twist in the story as Emodi becomes disappointed when his deputies appear before the supreme military council (SMC), they all denied the allegation. Jibo, in particular, concretized evidence and allegation against Emodi as being an incompetent boss. Jibo speaks thus: "Your Excellency, that's the most ridiculous allegation I have ever heard in my twenty-five years of service...The problem of leadership, your Excellency... When you have a director whose field officers are corrupt and instead of dealing with these officers, the director now turns round to accuse imaginary people, like the army, police and even the fire brigade... your Excellency, such a director to my mind is not fit to be a leader" (35). Consequent upon this allegation, the Customs boss, Emeka Emodi, is dismissed from service and replaced with Alhaji Jibo. Traumatized by the news of his dismissal, the Customs boss suddenly collapses and goes into coma. The author, through this, condemns the sudden dismissal of civil servants without due process. Mr Emodi is not given a fair hearing by the

military president, this act of autocratic governance and dictatorial leadership is anathema to good governance.

Okediran also raises the issue of revenge and high-level corruption in government. The death of Samuel and the unceremonious dismissal of Emodi necessitate Mrs. Gladys Emodi, wife of the erstwhile Customs boss, to revenge the death of her brother and the dismissal of her husband. She vehemently ensures that she deals with Alhaji Jibo, the new Director of Nigeria Customs Service whom she perceives to be responsible for her husband's misfortune, and Mr. Lati Baba, the chief smuggler, whom she also sees as the prime suspect of Samuel's death. It is against this backdrop that she plans with Maria, the secretary to Alhaji Jibo, to tape-record the director's illicit bargain with Lati Baba who has been arrested by Peter Ikoku and the smuggler's goods confiscated and taken to Ibadan.

Critical to the issue of arrest and confiscation is that the victims would always go free if they have strong connections in government or are able to negotiate their way out. This level of corruption is prevalent in Nigeria, especially among the uniformed men and civil servants. Lati Baba goes free because of his high connections in government. As a result, Peter Ikoku seeing the shady negotiation between his boss and the smuggler resigns from the Customs Service. Gladys Emodi successfully gets the tape-recorded discussion between Lati Baba and Jibo. On getting the tape, she also schematically decides to make merchandise of it. She informs Jibo of his discussion with Lati Baba and threatens to publish it if he refuses to part with twenty thousand naira as a ransom for buying the tape. Again, the Customs boss pays her with fake currency. One wonders what a Customs boss will be doing with fake currency, being an officer whose responsibility is to ensure that all contrabands are destroyed. This tells us that certain laws are meant to be obeyed only by the poor, while the makers of such laws blatantly break the law. Again, the fake currency also finds its way to the bank through a corrupt bank official who exchanges the counterfeit with the money in the bank vault, having bargained for twenty-five per cent. The author is irritated by this tralatitious corruption among Nigerians.

Having paid the ransom, Jibo is bewildered to read several newspaper headlines on bribe scandal by the Director of Nigerian Customs. Journalists on their part see the news as catchy and sensational; therefore, they persistently repeat the headline. As a result of the negative effects of the headline on government, the president gives Jibo an option to voluntarily resign or face outright dismissal. He accepts the option of soft landing by resigning from the service. Being able to achieve this feat, Gladys proceeds to get at Lati Baba, the suspected killer of Samuel. Various attempts made by Gladys to kill Lati Baba failed. Ajo, the slut who earlier attempts poisoning Lati Baba having witnessed the death of the assailant sent to kill Lati, and out of shock, becomes unconscious and she is rushed to the hospital. It is through Ajo while in the hospital that Lati Baba gets to know that the person who is after his life in Crossroad Hotel is the proprietress, Mrs. Gladys Emodi. With this revelation, Lati Baba and Gladys resolve their clandestine enmity by Lati Baba's open confession that Atere is the one behind the death of Samuel and has been taken care of by nature having died on his own. Gladys becomes remorseful for attempting to kill an innocent fellow.

Notwithstanding the turn of events, she counsels Lati Baba to quit the job of smuggling. This counsel makes Lati Baba ponders on his role as a smuggler. To him, no job is legitimate in Nigeria. “What of politicians who squandered our money. Are they not still gallivanting about with their ill-gotten wealth or the military? Are they any better? How much does a major general earn that has made many of them millionaires overnight?” (138). These thought-provoking questions are relevant in engaging on the voyage of good governance. Virtually everybody is involved in blending the bedlam of corruption. The man in the office is as corrupt as the man in the street. The confusion is so massive that one is tempted to join the crowd in accepting the trend as the norm. These devious acts in the system are the testament of woes, destruction and systemic decay in terms of derelict infrastructure and underdevelopment. One cannot afford to accept these but rather join voices with the author to condemn them in a bid to advocating good governance and altruistic leadership. True to this advocacy of good governance and change of orientation about the presupposed irredeemable decay in the system, Lati Baba, through the good counsel of Gladys, quits the hazardous job of smuggling. He buys over Crossroad Hotel from Gladys to be the new proprietor. Again, on her part, Gladys relocates to Lagos to meet her husband whose medical treatment abroad has been approved by the government and his initial dismissal converted to retirement.

Outside the issues of corruption and revenge, worthy of note in the text is that the author also vilifies tribal and ethnic sentiments. A great deal of the problems in Nigeria is tribal and ethnic sentiment against national interest. Nigerians sometimes are over-reactive when members of their tribe are being reprimanded for wrong-doing. They are often quick to speculate that a particular tribe is hated and another loved. Being caught in the web of bribery and chastised by the president, Jibo sails under false colour by casting aspersion on tribal dichotomy as the reason for his predicament. These flimsy excuses do not really hold sway as he is twisted with his own petard. The two people next in rank to him are northerners as the president observes. Jibo quickly interjects that southern politicians are responsible. This gets the president angry.

This tribal affiliation also designates some persons as untouchable, even when they commit heinous crimes. At the mention of one of the Emirs as one of the smugglers, Jibo and other officers from the north rebuff the conversation as they see it as sacrilegious to indict a traditional ruler. If credence is given to certain persons as sacred cows because of their traditional or religious position and are allowed to commit crime, then there is no transparency and responsiveness in governance. Everybody must be treated as equal before the law. Regrettably, the Nigerian system allows some persons to go with impunity even when they are caught in the act. This is unacceptable for a system that must thrive as the author tries to insinuate.

The language of this text foregrounds the author’s perception of Nigeria. His language delineates systemic corruption in the Customs Service. The language is emblematic of violence and social disorder. The opening incident in *The Boys at the Border* is a gory description of violence. “They got Samuel! He was shot about half an hour ago” (1). “... for the next moment, the driver squeezed the trigger and pumped some bullets into Superintendent Samuel”(3). These statements relate to the death of a Custom officer, Samuel,

who is killed by one of the smugglers. The incident in Crossroad Hotel between Lati Baba and the assailant sent to kill him is horrific. The author also employs the use of suspense as a veritable tool to retain the reader's consciousness. The revenge mission of Gladys Emordi over the demise of her brother and the dismissal of her husband retained a high degree of suspense. Although the use of suspense in this novel is not as visible as it is in *Strange Encounters* and *Tenants of the House*, which also detail systemic decay. The characters, except Emeka Emordi are all woven in one form of vice or another. The setting is Nigeria and the author captures the ills in the society.

In *The Upward Path*, Joseph Edoki raises critical issues that are germane to the growth and sustenance of democracy. He exposes the transformational impact of good governance on the citizenry and the economy of a nation. This transformational agenda as orchestrated by altruistic leadership; accentuates the commitment of President Fernando who has taken over the rein of power from corrupt leaders of Savannah as depicted in Edoki's second novel, *The African Dream*. Through his developmental clairvoyance and selflessness, he has been able to transform the country and also redirect the political and historical trajectory of Savannah. Mr. Gaga, a Rwandan-American and Ph.D. student from the United States of America has chosen Savannah as his research field having presumptuously surmised Africa to be one of the most backward continents. His research topic is ridiculously on "Why Africa is not developed". In his quest to finding a solution to his research, he meets the contrary. Beyond his expectation, the lifestyle of the Savanese where farmers such as Mrs. Nkomo and Mr. Bello own good cars, socialize in a five-star hotel and also have free access to minister and other political bigwigs is in contrast to his expectation. The agrarian, or what is called green revolution of Fernando, the technological breakthroughs and discoveries in sciences, the security in the country and the uninterrupted power supply, Gaga doubts the realities of these. At first, he thinks the people are feigning what they are not. Gaga's dissatisfaction over the information he gets from the Director-General of the National Planning Commission is shown in his conversation with his American friend over the phone:

And how is your project going?... I've met with the boss of the National Planning Commission... And what did you get from him? Lies, official lies, How? Blatant lies, bogus figures, incredible statistics, garbage,... that is the challenge of working in a developing country... What exactly did the director tell you? The man said there is no poverty in the country – no poverty at all.
(8)

To authenticate what he has heard and to clear his doubts, Gaga travels to various cities and villages to substantiate his findings on the transformation of Savannah, the revelations prove the same. His journey from Merigo to Yakabo to see Mr. Bello brings shocking revelations. Among the good things he sees in the country is that there are job vacancies everywhere without anybody to employ, a situation described as over employment. That is, there are jobs but everybody is employed. This is the direct opposite of unemployment. The standard of living in Greenville, a farming community in New Dodokido is high, a situation where farmers live in well-furnished apartments and ride in big cars such as Mr. Bello who drives a Toyota Land Cruiser Jeep.

Having been given a richly befitting welcome by the Bellos' which bespeaks of his wealth, Gaga surprisingly says, "American and European farmers can't even afford this. There must be something ugly underneath this beautiful scenery. Nobody can convince me that African farmers can afford such luxury flat"(22). In addition, Gaga's perplexity is also stemmed from the competition in technological discoveries with the appellation of genius given to those making invention and discoveries. This is against the celebration of mediocrity in Nigeria. In the agricultural sector, Genius Adamu discovers a new and improved breed of cassava that matures within eighty days. In car manufacturing, Genius Egbunike produces a lorry called Egbunike, while Genius Ewa and Ibisio discover solar power supply.

There are discoveries even in aeroplane manufacturing and more in Savannah. All these inventions are made possible through the efforts of government and encouragement of self-employed innovation. As a working system, power outage is strange in Savannah. In a particular instance; where the History teacher of Mirindi and Maranda, the Bellos' children mentions power failure, it sounds strange to them and they come home to ask their father. Candle and generator are also strange in Savannah. For over ten years, there has not been power failure. This is the dividend of good governance. The police and all other security agencies crave for excellence and good name in ensuring the good image of the country. As an organized society, Gaga is shocked to have been arrested for wandering on the street at about ten o'clock. "You were brought here because you were found on the street by 10: am - Looking this way, that way. What you were doing is very unusual. By ten everybody goes to work"(153). This shows that there is zero tolerance for laziness and idleness. The data of every citizen are in the database of the police and they adequately monitor everybody's movement. police in Savannah discharge their duties with utmost integrity without collecting bribes. Their desire according to the officer that spoke with Gaga is that: "we are interested in our image as an organization and the image of our country" (55).

In Savannah, there are no criminals and so the cells are empty. The police only spend their time to do counselling. These are indices of a highly sanitized society. As a result of this systemic sanity and development, Gaga decides to change his research topic, because to him Africa is already developed with zero corruption. The new proposed topic by Gaga is "How Africa can develop Africa". Although his supervisor rejects the new research proposal and insists on Gaga continuing his earlier topic, he makes up his mind to discontinue the programme in the United States and relocate to Savannah. This looks absurd to his friend, but based on the apparent developmental stride in Savannah, the security of lives and property, stable economy, technological innovation, sane electoral processes, stable power supply and political accountability and transparency, he decides to extend his three months visit to Savannah to pick a lecturing appointment in Apex University. As a way of indigenizing himself, he gets married to Ibisio. This acceptance of Africa as a home advances a discourse of white's acculturation by black model and style. "... I cannot continue to shy away from my convictions... Yes, my convictions ... I didn't believe a beautiful place peopled by beautiful people exist in this part of the world... Black is beautiful, so they say... Black is beautiful. Now I know... Now that I know, ..." (109). This self-conviction is a total acceptance of Africa in her pride of place. It is also a reversal model of the emblematic

problem of black migration to Europe and other western countries. Again, critical to this point is the issue of urban-rural migration in Savannah. This is against the known rural-urban migration. To this end, Edoki advances a trajectory of western migration to Africa orchestrated by good governance. He also authenticates that good governance attracts foreign investors and research.

As a way of curbing corruption, the bold inscription in various offices and Headlines is that: “Any rich man or woman whose source of wealth cannot be explained is a thief. If we stop honouring them, they will stop”(4). This is a pointer to the fact that the masses have a role to play in curbing corruption. A good example is the story of Money Miss Road, a corrupt fellow, who the authority of Apex University decides to confer an honorary doctorate degree. Having got hints of the award, some boys decide to buy a goat, dressed it in a convocation gown. While Money Miss Road marches to receive the award in the school pavilion, the boys also lead their goat and sing along side:

Ani man e wan be doctor

Ani man e come wear suit o!

Ani man e come wear tie o!

Animal in human skin. (38)

This goes viral and also brings the institution in a bad light. As a result, the senate regrets its action for honouring a man with a questionable character. It is, therefore, pertinent to note that, if our politicians are not celebrated for defrauding the masses, if public or political looters of national treasury are not ordained with ecclesiastical titles by religious leaders, if the church, mosque, traditional rulers and the masses reject their offerings and donations, they will change. If they see that they are now social pariah to their families, friends and the society at large, they will stop their corrupt practices. This is Edoki’s perception of institutionalizing good governance.

Edoki’s narrative style is commendable. He uses various literary techniques to complement his socio-political commitment in *The Upward Path*. The novel entails images of fruition and good governance. Edoki uses a thermal image of cold ambience to portray the radiance of good governance. The office of the National Planning Commission is typified with hope and goodly living. The waiting room is described thus: “The room was cold and quiet. The working of air conditioner was the only audible sound, and it excited the ear like a piece of instrumental music”(3). This paints a picture of a serene environment brought about by altruistic leadership and good governance. Edoki makes use of flashback to help refresh the minds of the readers on the African ugly past. The History teacher relates the dark old days of corruption and, bad leadership of Sir Afiam and Edgar Mollan through this technique. The use of flashback in this text mediates to juxtapose between the negative effects of bad governance and the positive impacts of good governance. As such, it helps to sustain the author’s ideology on good governance, which he foreshadows in Fernando’s dream as seen in the author’s earlier novel, the *African Dream*.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Okediran peeved by the systemic failure in Nigeria- has used his novel to agitate for a corruption free society. As a realist, he has portrayed the Nigerian system as it is. Edoki, on the other hand, has showcased the dividends of good governance and altruistic leadership. Though he paints an idealist world, through conscious efforts by Nigerians, it is possible to attain a similitude of it. It is, therefore, imperative to submit that good governance is achievable in Nigeria.

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